

Optimal allocation of wind production capacities in Poland - energy droughts minimization perspective

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Research question

Goal for expansion of onshore wind:

- How to optimally allocate the new capacities within the country?
- What is the range of potential for change of generation profile due to geographical allocation?
- How far is it possible to smoothen the production curve and decrease energy droughts?

Input data

Wind power generation:

- Source: ERA5, 100m wind speed
- Time scale: 2020-23, hourly
- Power curve: Vestas 3.45 MW
- Resolution: county level (powiat)

Land constrains:

- 8 MW/km²
- Excluded: forests, water, protected land
- Maximal number of turbines per county

Existing turbines:

- Open Street Map → Nr of turbines per county
- Follow same Vestas 3.45 profile
- Rescaled to capacity factor
- Subtracted from county potential

Method

The problem was solved with a Monte-Carlo method based on modified version of Modern Portfolio Theorem.

1 000 000 random portfolios:
How to add new turbines to existing?

Algorithm for i-th portfolio:

```
new = zeros(nr_of_loactions)
WHILE turbines_to_allocate > 0
  j = rand(0, nr_of_locations)
  n = rand(0, limit[j])
  inst = min(n, limit[j] - new[j])
  new[j] += inst
  turbines_to_allocate -= inst
```

Investigated portfolios:

- Maximal capacity factor (*best CF*)
- Maximal Sharpe Ratio (*CF/SD*)
- Minimalization of energy droughts (*max 10th percentile of CF*)
- Minimal standard deviation (*min SD*)

Results

All possible portfolios, investigated portfolios marked (↑)

Ordered CF curves for portfolios (↑)
Deviation from current ordered CF (↑)

Conclusion

- The potential for CF increase via new investments is limited, as best locations have already been used.
- Achievable potential of profile optimization:
 - $CF \in (0.37, 0.41)$
 - $SD \in (0.27, 0.29)$
- Best wind conditions are in the north, whereas counties at south and eastern border show the best complementarity.
- Max Sharpe scenario leads to 2 pp increase of production capacity of ordered capacity curve during the low wind hours.
- Benefits from geographical smoothing seem too low to implement incentives for specific, not market-optimized allocation.
- Range of potential is highly sensitive to land availability.

Portfolios in details

